

Funded by
the European Union

COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION PLAN FOR THE INNOVANTIBIOFILM PROJECT

Deliverable 6.1, December 2024

OUTPUT SUMMARY Project information	
Project Title	Boosting Sustainable Innovation in Developing New Antibiotic Adjuvants to Control Biofilm Resistance
Project Acronym	InnovAntiBiofilm
Call Identifier	HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-02-01
Grant Agreement Number	101157363
Starting Date	1 October 2024
End Date	30 September 2027
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Deliverable Title	D6.1 COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION PLAN
Deliverable Number	D6.1
Work Package	WP6 - Communication, Dissemination and Legacy
WP leader	Manuel SIMÕES (UPORTO)
Type	R — Document, report
Dissemination	PU - Public
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Date of Delivery	31/12/2024

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Date	16/12/2024

Acknowledgements

InnovAntiBiofilm has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Programme under Grant Agreement 101157363.

This document results from the contribution from *InnovAntiBiofilm* partners involved in Work Package 6 and all Work Package 6 leaders. We wish to acknowledge their invaluable contribution in all the different stages of the development progress. Special thanks to the European Commission for funding this ambitious programme.

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List of acronyms

AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
ANI	Portuguese National Innovation Agency
ASM	American Society for Microbiology
CDA	Communication and Dissemination Activities
CEA	Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives
CDE	Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation
EOD	Expected Outcomes of the Destination
EOT	Expected Outcomes of the Topic
ECCMID	Congress of the European Society of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases
ESCMID	European Society of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases
EU	European Union
IP	Intellectual Property
POPD	Protection of Personal Data
RDI	Research, Development, and Innovation
REA	European Research Executive Agency
UPORTO	University of Porto
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan (CDE) for the *InnovAntiBiofilm* project is a strategic framework designed to maximize the societal, economic, and scientific impact of the HORIZONWIDERA-2023-ACCESS-02-01 Twinning call. *InnovAntiBiofilm* focuses on the sustainable development of new adjuvant agents to boost the action of antibiotics against biofilm infections. This will be achieved through the sustainable biosynthesis of plant molecules and the rational development of derivatives. These scientific activities, together with capacity building and networking activities, talent development of young researchers, mentoring, inclusiveness, and strengthening research management and administration skills, will be at the crux of the project concept. This plan outlines specific approaches to raise awareness, foster collaboration, and facilitate the uptake of project findings across various stakeholder groups.

Key objectives of the CDE plan include engaging scientific, industrial, policy-making, and public audiences through tailored messaging and multi-channel communication. Targeted efforts will ensure visibility for *InnovAntiBiofilm*, promote knowledge transfer to industry and academia, and strengthen collaboration across the EU research ecosystem. Communication channels will include a dedicated project website, social media, workshops, open-access publications, newsletters and press releases, all of which serve to increase accessibility to project outcomes and engage stakeholders effectively.

Exploitation strategies focus on developing intellectual property (IP) management plans, aligning innovations with market needs, and fostering projects that drive commercialization of project outputs. Early integration of industry stakeholders will help position the project outcomes for market adoption, while policy briefs will support the alignment of findings with relevant regulatory frameworks.

This document outlines the approach for the CDE of the *InnovAntiBiofilm* project. The CDE plan will be implemented by UPORTO as the lead beneficiary under Work Package 6, "Communication, Dissemination, and Legacy," with active participation from all project partners. This plan establishes specific CDE objectives, tools, key messages, and target audiences, aiming to position *InnovAntiBiofilm* as a catalyst for advancing sustainable biofilm resistance solutions. By promoting cutting-edge research and innovation, the plan supports European and international policy frameworks, including the European Project "One Health Action Plan" against Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) and contributes to the objectives of the "Pharmaceutical Strategy" for Europe. Additionally, the document includes mechanisms for continuous monitoring and evaluation through key performance indicators (KPIs), ensuring adaptability and responsiveness to stakeholder feedback and project developments. Data protection and ethical considerations are integral to all activities, ensuring transparency and compliance with EU regulations.

This document is a "living document" and shall be revisited and updated throughout *InnovAntiBiofilm* lifetime to adapt to emerging needs, activities and tools. The data provided by indicators will be used to guide partners in the revision process of the DCE plan. At the end of the *InnovAntiBiofilm* Project lifetime, the project final report will include an updated and final version of the CDE plan that will allow the European Commission to assess the impact of the Project.

Introduction

The European Commission, through the launch of Horizon Europe, aims to invigorate European Research, Development, and Innovation (RDI) projects, fostering systemic advancements through collaborative efforts among public and private entities. The *InnovAntiBiofilm* project, comprising four leading institutions, aligns with Horizon Europe's strategic orientation "Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area," specifically targeting the sustainable development of antibiotic adjuvants to address biofilm resistance challenges in healthcare. This project is part of the Cluster "Widening Participation and Spreading Excellence".

InnovAntiBiofilm's vision is to drive systemic change across the research-to-innovation pipeline, integrating sustainable biosynthesis and combinatorial chemistry to create effective solutions against biofilm-related infections. By strengthening collaboration among EU partners, the project supports European and global health policy goals, including the European Project "One Health Action Plan" against AMR, the objectives of the Pharmaceutical Strategy for Europe, and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UN SDGs), particularly SDG 3 "Good Health and Well-being" and SDG 9 "Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure". The CDE plan defines *InnovAntiBiofilm's* strategy for engaging diverse audiences, promoting knowledge transfer, and ensuring uptake of project outcomes. This plan considers the following priorities:

- *InnovAntiBiofilm's* short-, medium-, and long-term objectives (specific, operational, and general);
- Core messages that communicate the project's impact on sustainable healthcare and biotechnology solutions;
- Effective channels and tools for communication, dissemination, and exploitation among partners;
- Potential end-users and industries that will benefit from the project's findings;
- Monitoring and evaluation metrics for CDE activities; and
- Compliance with data privacy regulations to protect personal data.

This strategy builds on the successes of previous EU initiatives, drawing from valuable experience in project communication and stakeholder engagement to enhance research visibility, forward-thinking planning, and international collaboration. The CDE activities will maintain informed engagement with stakeholders, project funders, the research community, and the public, highlighting collaboration opportunities and sharing progress toward project objectives.

1. Objectives and expected impacts of the communication, dissemination & exploitation plan

InnovAntiBiofilm presents a myriad of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, aiming at successfully engaging with relevant stakeholders to guarantee the sustainability of the project after its completion. *InnovAntiBiofilm* comprises a Work Package (WP) exclusively dedicated to Communication and Dissemination (WP6) and two tasks (T2.1, T2.2) directed at the exploitation of results. The communication strategy proposed herein will seek to maximize the visibility and impact of all actions foreseen under *InnovAntiBiofilm*. An effective dissemination strategy will enable the results to reach the targeted audience and cause scientific, societal impacts and help shifting the status quo of the participating organizations.

The communication activities outlined in the plan will serve as the foundation for: i) setting short-term and long-term communication goals and assessing potential impacts; ii) establishing multilateral communication channels between the project management team and stakeholders; iii) defining responsibilities and creating a timeline for carrying out communication actions.

InnovAntiBiofilm will make use of the free-of-charge services designed by the EC, such as the Open Research Europe Platform (dissemination), Horizon Results Platform (dissemination), Horizon Results Platform TV (communication), Horizon Results Booster (dissemination and exploitation), European Standardisation Booster (dissemination and exploitation), and Innovation radar (dissemination and exploitation).

1.1. Definitions

Communication, dissemination, and exploitation are key components of *InnovAntiBiofilm's* outreach strategy, each serving to maximize the project's visibility, accessibility, and impact. Definitions and objectives are clarified below in Figure 1.

Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation	
<p>“Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.”</p> <p>(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)</p>	<p>“The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.”</p> <p>(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)</p>	<p>“The utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.”</p> <p>(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)</p>	 Definition
<p>Reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of EU-funded R&I activities, e.g. by addressing and providing possible solutions to fundamental societal challenges.</p>	<p>Transfer knowledge & results with the aim to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximising the impact of EU-funded research.</p>	<p>Effectively use project results through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes aiming to turn R&I actions into concrete value and impact for society.</p>	 Objective
<p>Inform about and promote the project AND its results/success.</p>	<p>Describe and ensure results available for others to USE → focus on results only!</p>	<p>Make concrete use of research results (not restricted to commercial use.)</p>	 Focus
<p>Multiple audiences beyond the project’s own community incl. media and the broad public.</p>	<p>Audiences that may take an interest in the potential USE of the results (e.g. scientific community, industrial partner, policymakers).</p>	<p>People/organisations including project partners themselves that make concrete use of the project results, as well as user groups outside the project.</p>	 Target Audience

Figure 1 - Extract from the European IPR Helpdesk - Making the most of your Horizon 2020 Project

1.2. Communication, dissemination and exploitation objectives

The CDE activities will amplify *InnovAntiBiofilm’s* impact by ensuring visibility across multiple levels and audiences. The objectives align with Horizon Europe’s emphasis on collaborative innovation, facilitating both short- and long-term engagement with stakeholders. The following sections outline the project’s operational, specific, and general objectives.

1.2.1. Operational objectives (short term)

- Provide a continuous stream of project updates, research outcomes, and developments to relevant stakeholders at the local, national, and international levels.
- Develop and distribute accessible communication materials about *InnovAntiBiofilm’s* research, milestones, and results.
- Engage stakeholders from the project’s early stages, tailoring solutions to meet industry, academic, and regulatory needs.
- Customize messaging to suit audience demographics, ensuring accessibility and relevance.

- Center communication efforts around impactful results rather than processes.

1.2.2. Specific objectives (medium term)

- Enhance visibility and understanding of *InnovAntiBiofilm's* goals, emphasizing the relevance of biofilm research to policymakers, healthcare professionals, and industry leaders.
- Employ clear, accessible language to bridge the gap between complex science and public comprehension, creating people-centered narratives around antibiotic resistance and biofilm control.
- Foster collaborative networks that support the efficient adoption of project outcomes, promoting evidence-based knowledge transfer between the scientific community and end-users.

1.2.3. General objectives or expected impacts (long term)

- Influence healthcare policy to support biofilm-related research and sustainable antimicrobial practices.
- Disseminate research insights to a broader audience, enhancing public understanding of biofilm resistance.
- Foster increased public awareness and proactive involvement in sustainable healthcare, specifically in managing biofilm-related infections.
- Strengthen Europe's capacity in sustainable biofilm R&D&I by fostering global projects and information-sharing networks.
- Facilitate widespread knowledge transfer and application of *InnovAntiBiofilm's* findings for industry and healthcare sectors to benefit from innovative biofilm control solutions.

Exploitation activities within *InnovAntiBiofilm* will align with overarching policy goals, including the European Research Area (ERA) roadmap, the New European Innovation Agenda, as well as contribute to achieving United Nations SDGs related to health and innovation.

1.3. Communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy

The communication and dissemination strategy has been defined to target different groups, being designed for each specific audience, and taking advantage of the appropriate platform: targeted messages, means and language. Outreach activities entail communication initiatives directed to the general public, rather than specifically to the research community or other stakeholders: the objective is to create awareness among the general public about *InnovAntiBiofilm* (technology and social outcomes), while equally stressing its implications for Europe and its citizens. The CDE encompasses a set of actions to disseminate the non-confidential results generated during the project to ensure that as many relevant audiences as possible have access to these results. The plan is to enhance awareness about the tangible and intangible outputs of *InnovAntiBiofilm*, to contribute to knowledge building and advancement of innovation in Europe as well as to prevent duplicity of research work. Considering the great influence and the broad coverage that digital media achieves nowadays, the first channels to be implemented will be the project website, Twitter (i.e., X) and LinkedIn accounts. *InnovAntiBiofilm* website will collect information about the overall communication activities allowing common stream of information, newsletters, press releases, infographics, factsheets, and training materials. The media coverage in press releases will also be part of the project communication plan - each partner will be responsible for communicating to their regional media and propagate *InnovAntiBiofilm's* vision and technological innovation. As for dissemination, the partners will implement (individually and jointly)

their participation in relevant external events and produce scientific publications. The partners will be vocal about the project, being committed to engage with the public and always acknowledging the financial support from the EU.

InnovAntiBiofilm has an intrinsic value of exploitable solutions. Strategic measures will be put in place to accomplish the exploitation objectives, such as seeking i) projects with private investors (T2.2), ii) feasible financing avenues, iii) follow-up R&D projects at regional and international level, iv) cooperation with industry, v) development of policy briefs and recommendations. The tangible deliverable will be a Technology Exploitation Roadmap (D2.2) delivered by KPMG at M36, where exploitation avenues will be duly analyzed.

2. Key messages

Arising from the *InnovAntiBiofilm*'s general, specific and operational objectives listed in Section 1, a set of key messages have been defined, as the basis for a deeper approach to specific target audiences. **Key messages correspond to the main points of information to get across; they are set out to guide the CDE orientation of the Project.**

Key messages to be delivered to society at large on the need for **biofilm and AMR R&D&I**:

- AMR is a growing global health crisis that threatens the effectiveness of antibiotics against microbial pathogens.
- Sustainable solutions for biofilm control are crucial to enhance long-term healthcare outcomes and prevent recurrent and persistent infections.
- Integrating biofilm R&D&I into healthcare and industry is essential for developing market-ready, effective treatments.

Combating AMR requires international collaboration and knowledge-sharing to drive innovative and sustainable solutions. The following messages will guide all *InnovAntiBiofilm* communication channels:

- **Advancing Solutions to Combat AMR:** *InnovAntiBiofilm* is developing innovative and sustainable solutions to tackle biofilm resistance, a major driver of antimicrobial resistance, which impacts both human health and environmental sustainability.
- **Delivering Innovations on Natural Antibiofilm agents:** The project is focused on creating new antibiofilm agents derived from plant-based compounds, offering effective eco-friendly alternatives to traditional antibiotics and reducing environmental impact.
- **Empowering European Research Excellence:** By enhancing collaboration between academia and industry, *InnovAntiBiofilm* strengthens Europe's leadership in research, ensuring impactful, science-based healthcare innovations.
- **Sustainability at the Core:** Through its innovative approaches, *InnovAntiBiofilm* supports the global transition to sustainable healthcare systems by reducing reliance on synthetic chemical-based treatments and leveraging natural resources as a sustainable source of bioactive compounds.

3. Target audiences: stakeholders, network groups

This chapter details key target audiences for *InnovAntiBiofilm*. Each particular target group must be addressed with information tailored to its interests and through the channels best suiting the purpose of information delivery. Given the wide variety of stakeholders and organizational modes of stakeholders, section 3.1 offers a short definition to clarify each of the concepts presented in this chapter.

3.1. Definitions

- **Target audience:** It is a group of persons to whom messages are addressed.
- **Stakeholders:** can be defined as people, groups or organisations having an active role because of their interest in the activities of the Project, e.g., European Commission, Funding Agencies and others.

- **Policy makers:** individuals or groups responsible for creating, evaluating, and implementing policies within government, organizations, or institutions. They may hold roles in legislative, executive, or regulatory bodies at various levels (local, national, or international) and work to address societal issues, promote public welfare, and guide actions within their scope of influence. In the context of research and development, policymakers play a key role in shaping regulations, funding priorities, and strategic frameworks that influence scientific progress, public health, environmental sustainability, and economic development.
- **Networks:** can be defined as list of contacts that, even if they do not have an active role in the programme, can contribute to the wide communication and dissemination of activities. Networks can be of different types. They can be political, administrative, and union networks, for instance, linked to opinion leaders, media, and social media influencers. Building upon the experience accumulated by KPMG, the InnovAntiBiofilm Project always has numerous contacts with a wide range of scientific and industrial networks.

3.2. General aim of target audiences

Identifying and categorising target audiences is essential for crafting specific, impactful messages tailored to their communication preferences. This approach ensures the project reaches not only stakeholders within the AMR scientific community but also a broader audience, including citizens, policymakers, and industry professionals.

The general aims of audience segmentation and engagement are to:

- Ensure alignment of communication objectives with the goals and priorities of project partners, fostering a unified strategy.
- Facilitate effective exchange of information between diverse stakeholder groups, enabling collaboration and shared understanding of project outcomes.
- Develop and share best practices for communication methodologies within the project, ensuring consistency and coherence in messaging.
- Coordinate activities for open data and open access, with researchers and designated “Contact Points” ensuring transparency and accessibility of project findings.
- Implement robust monitoring and evaluation frameworks, enabling the measurement of communication activities and their impact.

By aligning audience-specific communication strategies with the overall objectives of InnovAntiBiofilm, the project enhances its ability to disseminate results widely and foster meaningful engagement across diverse sectors.

3.3. Identified audiences

The main identified target groups addressed in this plan are: **scientific communities, including networks, policy makers, authorities, citizens, and industry**. For each of these groups, this plan establishes their relevance and specific CDE activities of interest (Table 1).

Table 1. The main exploitable results of InnovAntiBiofilm

Target Group(s)	Details	Relevance	Communication and Dissemination Methods	KPIs
1. Biotechnological and Pharmaceutical Industry Professionals	Professionals (Chemists, Pharmacists, Biotechnologists, Chemical and Biological Engineers) who are dedicated/inclined to actively use metabolic engineering or bio-based technologies for phytochemical production	Awareness of the application and practical use of the technology, benefits of the technology, and alignment with market needs	Industry workshops, technology demonstrations, case studies	Number of workshops held, number of participants, number of inquiries from industry
2. Research Institutions Academia/ Researchers	Organisations performing research and innovation in metabolic engineering, fine and combinatorial chemistry, and antimicrobial drug development; Relevant networks of researchers; Research groups working on drug development, biofilms research, combinatorial chemistry, bioprocess engineering, metabolic engineering	Mutual learning to enhance the level of research excellence; collaborations for the uptake of the technological advances	Peer-reviewed journal articles, academic conferences, project-specific workshops	Number of publications, citations, and new research collaborations initiated
3. Students and Junior Researchers	Biotechnology, Bioengineering, Chemistry, Microbiology and Pharmaceutical Sciences students and young researchers who seek to improve their knowledge and research capabilities in the field	Building capacity and fostering a skilled community in bioprocess engineering and advanced combinatorial chemistry to drive innovative antimicrobial development; promoting collaborative learning to elevate research excellence	Training sessions, mentorship programmes, participation in project events	Number of students trained, feedback scores from participants, participation metrics
4. Policy Makers	National and European authorities governing health, economy, and regulatory frameworks for pharmaceuticals	Information on the drivers, requirements, and barriers of the sector at national and European levels; encouraging policies supporting biofilm-resistant innovations	Policy briefs, stakeholder meetings, high-level roundtables, white papers	Number of policy briefs delivered, meetings held, and policymakers engaged
5. Industry	Industrial Stakeholders (Biotechnological, Pharmaceutical and Fine-chemistry industries) seeking cutting edge technologies and scientific advances to enhance their processes	Expert support to escalating the technology and sector; investment opportunities (spin-offs)	Joint research opportunities, market-oriented presentations	Number of partnerships formed

6. Media	News & Digital Media channels focused on health, biotechnology, and sustainability topics	Platforms to widely communicate the main findings	Press releases, interviews, media kits, and project success stories	Number of press releases published, media mentions, and audience reach metrics
7. Citizens	General public, with an emphasis on raising awareness of phytochemical-based innovations and the importance of combating antimicrobial resistance responsibly	Raising awareness about AMR and promoting a responsible antibiotic use through simple, engaging communication	Social media campaigns, infographics, blogs, public webinars	Social media engagement (likes, shares, comments), webinar attendance, feedback received

InnovAntiBiofilm is designed to fully achieve all the five Expected Outcomes of the Topic (EOT) and Expected Outcomes of the Destination (EOD) outlined in the HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-02-01 topic. These impacts will be evaluated at the end of the project (2027) and again two years after post-completion (2029), to assess long-term sustainability and effectiveness. The target groups, pathways, and impact types to achieving the proposed project results are described below in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2. Expected Outcomes of the Topic (EOT) | Pathway | Target Group | Type of Impact (Scientific, Economic, Technologic, Societal)

Expected Outcomes of the Topic and How InnovAntiBiofilm Responds
<p><i>EOT1: Improved excellence capacity and resources in Widening countries (...)</i></p> <p>PATHWAY: <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i> is based on a consortium of excellence, which will jointly ensure the development of innovative solutions for antibiotic resistance through sustainable and advanced technologies. Several activities (WP2-WP6) will be organised to ensure the sharing of outstanding technology, resources and knowledge between the Widening and non-Widening partners. Technology exploitation, IPR management and interaction with relevant stakeholders and industry are also part of the work plan (T2.1). The project will contribute to develop a R&I core in Portugal in metabolic and bioprocess engineering for advanced production of phytochemical molecules, and for their rational optimisation through parallel synthesis for a boosted therapeutic effect. This is an innovative technological approach in the EU to overcome the costs and reduced yields when searching for phytochemicals from crude plant extracts and to reinvent the antimicrobial pipeline in response to the global crisis of antibiotic-resistant infections. This strategy has the potential to position Portugal and specifically UPORTO, as an EU reference in the antimicrobial drug development field. The project will boost UPORTO competitiveness and internationalisation, promoting the interest and the opportunities to become a host institution for ERC and MSCA grantees and increasing UPORTO participation in EU projects in biofilm research, medicinal chemistry and metabolic engineering fields, as well as the cooperation with industrial stakeholders to exploit the project results and to establish collaborative research. The pathway will lead to an increase in the success in securing international funding, more publications in journals with high impact factor and an increase in patenting innovative antimicrobial therapeutic products. TARGET GROUP: Academia, Junior and Senior Researchers, Policy Makers, Industry. IMPACT: Scientific, Economic, Technologic.</p>
<p><i>EOT2: Enhanced strategic networking activities between (...) Widening countries and at least two internationally-leading (...)</i></p> <p>PATHWAY: <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i> will clearly instigate collaborative research among Widening and non-Widening partners. Networking activities (WP3: expert visits, thematic workshops, summer/winter schools) are in place to strategically mitigate the weaknesses found at UPORTO with the goal of promoting the development of strong and solid research through knowledge-transfer activities, based on the strengths of all the different partners. Staff exchange actions (T3.2), both scientific and administrative, and a mentoring programme (T4.2) - ensuring that at least 6 young researchers from UPORTO will have the possibility to be mentored by experts from non-Widening partners - will be in place to spur knowledge sharing. The participation in at least 2 relevant industry events, 6 international conferences, and 2 brokerage events as well as the development of 1 roadmap of future EU-funding collaboration are also important networking-related activities. The pathway will lead to more advanced training of researchers in emerging R&D for establishing high-quality new knowledge, thus fostering diffusion of</p>

<p>knowledge. TARGET GROUP: Biotech/Pharma Professionals, Junior and Senior Researchers, Industry. IMPACT: Scientific, Technologic, Societal.</p>
<p><i>EOT3: Raised reputation, research profile and attractiveness of the coordinating institution from the Widening country (...)</i></p>
<p>PATHWAY: UPORTO has a strong research profile on the development and testing of innovative antimicrobial strategies based on natural molecules. However, in <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i>, UPORTO will benefit from the expertise and know-how of CEA on the rational modification of molecular properties of phytochemicals for improved activity against biofilms. UPORTO will also benefit from Fraunhofer IME application-oriented research and the expertise on metabolic engineering and cell factories, specifically on the development and implementation of de novo biosynthetic pathways to the engineered host cells aiming a sustainable and augmented production of specific phytochemicals. This is essential to increase the profitability of the exploitation of new molecules, increasing the interest for industrial partners and contributing to the development of innovative bioprocesses while meeting industrial production standards in the EU. KPMG will have an important role on the interaction between the academy and the industry and on the exploitation of results and competences. This collaboration and the sharing of expertise will allow the implementation of a new research agenda at UPORTO: it will allow the development of a new research line boosting the innovation in natural solutions for the antibiotic resistance crisis. The application of advanced metabolic and bioprocess engineering for heterologous phytochemical production is a completely new goal for UPORTO. The implementation of metabolic engineering for building optimised cell factories will reinforce the UPORTO biotechnology research competences with completely new scientific capacity. In combination with the new expertise on medicinal and combinatorial chemistry, <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i> will contribute to the international recognition of UPORTO as an institution able to develop new antimicrobial therapeutic molecules targeting specific microbial phenotypes (from a sustainable biosynthesis, optimisation of molecular properties, and validation of antimicrobial therapeutic effects). The work to be undertaken under WPs 2-5 will directly and successfully contribute to the enhancement of research and development skills of UPORTO's staff, based on the cultivation of research capacity, networking and nurturing young research talents. The pathway will lead to strengthening human capital in R&D&I and build-up of scientific reputation to attract international researchers. TARGET GROUP: Academia, Junior and Senior Researchers. IMPACT: Scientific, Technologic.</p>
<p><i>EOT4: Strengthened research management capacities and administrative skills of the staff (...)</i></p>
<p>PATHWAY: <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i> will be instrumental to strengthen the research management capacities and administrative skills at UPORTO as it will provide them the opportunity of closely working, and be trained, by a large and specialised firm in the field (KPMG, T3.5) and the chance of research administrators to be seconded at research administration departments at CEA and Fraunhofer IME (T3.2) for two weeks. This activity directly contributes to building capacity on funding, research management, and technology transfer, thus impacting the success rate and participation of UPORTO in EU-funding projects. The pathway will lead to the uptake of R&I in society, economy and science through high-impact diffusion of knowledge while addressing EU policy priorities & global challenges through R&I, together with an increase in success in securing international highly competitive funding. TARGET GROUP: Academia, Junior and Senior Researchers. IMPACT: Scientific, Technologic.</p>
<p><i>EOT5: Improved creativity supported by development of new approaches in Research and Innovation collaboration (...)</i></p>
<p>PATHWAY: <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i> is defined by activities dedicated to the development of R&I skills of qualified scientists, also aiming at the development of R&I activities to define a complete pipeline for the development of phytochemical-based antibiofilm therapeutic molecules through innovative metabolic engineering approaches and parallel synthesis. Mobility of researchers is encouraged (T3.2), which will result in the mobility of at least 2 post-doctoral researchers and 2 PhD students from UPORTO to CEA and Fraunhofer IME and <i>vice versa</i> (UPORTO will receive 2 researchers from both non-Widening institutions). Additionally, T6.3 focuses on the definition of a roadmap for future EU-funding collaboration, which includes possible collaborations under ERASMUS+ programme, thus finding other vehicles for the circulation of excellent researchers and students. The pathway will lead to the creation of high-quality and high-impact new knowledge, thus strengthening human capital in R&D&I, while spreading excellence. TARGET GROUP: Academia, Junior and Senior Researchers. IMPACT: Scientific, Technologic.</p>

Table 3. Expected Outcomes of the Destination (EOD) | Pathway | Target Group | Type of Impact (scientific, economic, technological, societal)

Expected Outcomes of the Destination How InnovAntiBiofilm Responds
<p>EOD1: Increased science and innovation capacity for all actors in the R&I system in Widening countries</p> <p>PATHWAY: <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i> includes a well-defined pack of activities to stimulate a place-based evolution of the R&I ecosystem of the Widening country. The project will provide the tools to increase the excellence of science and innovation in Northern Portugal by capacitating (technologically and administratively) the most important regional HEI. Networking, development of a strategic research agenda, training on research, management, administrative and technology transfer skills, which include all R&I actors, specifically young researchers, undergraduate and PhD students, qualified scientists, research administration and management staff, but also related industry and stakeholders as well as educational institutions are key examples of how <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i> will impact the regional R&I ecosystem. The pathway will lead to the enhancement of R&D activities at UPORTO, with a correspondent increase in the number of researchers, publications, patents, together with the acquisition of competences from leading institutions to establish high-level research in emerging areas (<i>i.e.</i>, medicinal chemistry and metabolic engineering). TARGET GROUP: Academia, Junior, Senior Researchers, Industry. IMPACT: Scientific, Technologic, Economic.</p>
<p>EOD2: Structural changes leading to modernised and more competitive R&I systems in eligible countries</p> <p>PATHWAY: A pipeline of activities, based on the sharing of advanced technologies and resources from all partners (WP2-WP5), will contribute to the establishment of a more modern and competitive R&I system in Northern Portugal. It will apply novel approaches combining fundamental sciences and applied research, thus spurring the development of advanced techniques for the development of antibiotic boosters from plants, using metabolic engineering to enable the heterologous production of specific phytochemicals in bioreactors instead of harvesting plants, and parallel synthesis for the fine-tune of molecular properties. The pathway will lead to an increased impact in the number and quality of publications and the potential to generate innovation, leveraging investments in R&I, contributing to an education and research more in tune with the potential of the country/region. TARGET GROUP: Academia, Junior and Senior Researchers, Policy Makers, Industry. IMPACT: Scientific, Technologic, Economic, Societal.</p>
<p>EOD3: Reformed R&I systems and institutions leading to increased attractiveness and retention of research talents</p> <p>PATHWAY: <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i> is seen as pivotal in creating a place-based evolution of biotechnology and medicinal chemistry in the region. The creation of conditions to retain and recruit talent is vital. By capacitating UPORTO, <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i> will set the foundations for the region to be fully capable of retaining the best talent and to attract excellence researchers from other regions. T4.3 will define a joint agenda on how UPORTO can recruit ERC and MSCA grantees to establish themselves at UPORTO. <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i> is focused on the exploitation of results, not exclusively in the analysis of their commercial potential but also a significant focus on possible additional benefits and spill-over effects to the society and the industry, such as: policy briefs/recommendations, development of competences or existing capabilities of the research groups and retention of highly skilled researchers to boost fundamental and applied research. The pathway will lead to the establishment of a high-level research environment in antimicrobial drug development to retain and attract international reputed researchers. TARGET GROUP: Academia, Junior and Senior Researchers, Industry. IMPACT: Scientific, Technologic, Economic, Societal.</p>
<p>EOD4: Mobilisation of national and EU resources for strategic investments</p> <p>PATHWAY: <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i> is fully aligned with the regional S3. As such, investment in biotechnology and medicinal chemistry will contribute to improve innovation capacity and the integration of new knowledge in the national context. Consequently, it will develop the necessary competences to expand novel approaches aligned with industrial trends and societal needs, which in turn will contribute to national and regional interests. Given that EU Structural Funds are fully aligned with the regional S3, the mobilisation of resources will be facilitated via <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i>. Stakeholders working together will boost the mobilisation of resources, contributing to the creation of a joint critical mass in the region. This will also directly impact the amount of EU-funding raised for R&I. The pathway will lead to the mobilisation of the most relevant local and EU actors in terms of science, technology and innovation, and linking it with world-class level international partners and focusing on emergent areas of medicinal chemistry and biotechnology, together with an alignment with strategic S3 priorities for the three regions of the consortium, thus increasing the capacity to raise competitive funding via Structural Funds. TARGET GROUP: Bio and Pharma Professionals, Academia, Senior and Junior Researchers, Policy Makers, Industry. IMPACT: Scientific, Technologic, Economic, Societal.</p>
<p>EOD5: Higher participation success in Horizon Europe and more consortium leadership roles</p> <p>PATHWAY: According to data from the Portuguese National Innovation Agency (ANI)¹, Portugal has a H2020 success rate of 14.3% (above the EU average of 12.9%). Although these figures may sound encouraging, one of the hindrances that Widening countries face is the access to funding. <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i> will create a consolidated European network with excellent and complementary skills in biotechnology and medicinal chemistry for specialized antimicrobial development, which will increase</p>

¹ [Portugal Exceeds One Billion Euro Target of European Funding in H2020 | ANI](#)

<p>the participation and funding from EU-funding programmes in organisations in the Northern Region of the country. The combination of networking (T3.1, T3.2, T6.3 – workshops, summer/winter schools, secondments, symposium) with training for young researchers (T4.1), and the strengthening of administration capacities of UPORTO (T3.5), will ensure the promotion of joint EU-funding collaborations, contributing directly to higher participation success in Horizon Europe and to stimulate the participation as consortium leaders. Also, the presence of experienced partners in the consortium is an added-value in terms of sharing of expertise and best practices in how to access and manage EU-funding grants. TARGET GROUP: Academia, Senior and Junior Researchers. IMPACT: Scientific, Technologic.</p>
<p><i>EOD6: Stronger links between academia and business and improved career permeability</i></p>
<p>PATHWAY: T2.1 will be solely dedicated to the cooperation with industry, to validate research findings, to scale-up innovation, to promote the access to the necessary distribution channels, and to align research objectives with market needs and industry trends. The identification of strategic stakeholders (pharmaceutical, chemical and biotechnological industry, complementary research groups, regulatory entities, educational institutions) is a specific goal of WP2. InnovAntiBiofilm will directly result in stronger links and collaborations between academia and business, via the establishment of memoranda of understanding, collaboration protocols or joint funded projects. Industrial stakeholders will be actively engaged from the beginning, as they will be challenged to be part of the networking activities (WP3 and WP6) and to actively take part in them. The consortium also relies on the expertise of a large corporate player (KPMG) who will facilitate and promote interactions with the industry and share their expertise in dealing with a vast array of businesses. Also, T2.3 and T3.6, via the definition of a joint strategy for post-project collaboration relying on EU-funding, will seek to apply to MSCA Doctoral Networks. Together, these initiatives will not only enable the increase of links between academia and business, but they will also allow the placement of excellent researchers in an industrial setting. The pathway will contribute to increase of employment in knowledge-intensive services that currently employ only 22.94% of the region’s total workforce, well below the country’s average (26.99%) and EU27 average (35.32%) TARGET GROUP: Bio & Pharma Professionals, Academia, Industry. IMPACT: Scientific, Technologic, Economic, Societal.</p>
<p><i>EOD7: Strengthened role of the Higher Education sector in research and innovation</i></p>
<p>PATHWAY: InnovAntiBiofilm, via the investment in personnel, critical mass, creation of a more inclusive research environment, and strengthened capacity to raise and manage funding, will be a vital player to increase the R&I capacity of HEIs in the region. The spill-over effects will be clear in the sense that regional stakeholders will be actively involved in the different networking actions and the envisioned communication and dissemination plan will make sure that everyone is included in the process. Also, UPORTO and CEA/UPSACLAY are part of EUGLOH (European University Alliance for Global Health): a consortium of researchers and students for the development of interdisciplinary activities, particularly in education and training related to Global Health. InnovAntiBiofilm will benefit from an already well-defined strategy for the strength of HEI sector in R&I and it will provide a huge opportunity to create a smaller consortium among the 4 partners to synergistically work on the engagement of higher education sectors and on the dissemination of the project for degree and master students. In that way, InnovAntiBiofilm will create a robust linkage between academia, business and R&D centres. Moreover, the planned workshops and training sessions have as target public undergraduate students, specifically at UPORTO and CEA, who both are educational institutions. The pathway will lead to an increase of the levels of business lab-based research and increase the incentives for patenting on the academia/research side through the generation of high-impact translational research, together with the quadruple helix of innovation looped in and working together towards long-term plan to promote a bold agenda of significant institutional change in R&I. TARGET GROUP: Academia, Senior and Junior Researchers, Policy Makers. IMPACT: Scientific, Technologic, Economic.</p>
<p><i>EOD8: Greater involvement of regional actors in the R&I process</i></p>
<p>PATHWAY: InnovAntiBiofilm is deeply consistent with Regional S3 for Northern Portugal (Health and Life Sciences and Agro-Environmental and Food System), Île-de-France and Nordrhein-Westfalen (Complex Systems Engineering and Software, Environmental & Circular Economy, Innovative Medicine, Health & Life Science), and it will prompt S3 strategies of three different, yet complementary EU region, thus contributing to the regional change of <i>status quo</i> in terms of R&I. The positioning of all HEIs in their regional ecosystem (important R&I players) will facilitate the involvement of regional actors in the R&I transformation. The main regional stakeholders (quadruple helix of innovation: educational institutions, industry, services, regulatory entities and governmental institutions) will be identified (T2.1/T6.1), and the communication and networking among strategic regional stakeholders will be promoted along the organised events. It is expected that these networking activities promote the discussion of regional needs and the dissemination of scientific and results that may contribute for boosting regional innovation. The pathway will lead to the development of innovative and impactful research while ensuring diffusion of knowledge and Open Science for uptake of R&I in local actors. TARGET GROUP: Academia, Industry, Policy Makers, Citizens. IMPACT: Scientific, Technologic, Economic, Societal.</p>
<p><i>EOD9: Improved outreach to international level for all actors</i></p>
<p>PATHWAY: InnovAntiBiofilm activities will result in the development of a consolidated and multidisciplinary international network. The project impacts will strengthen the collaboration among partners and stakeholders creating a core EU network highly specialised in the development of innovative natural strategies for microbial biofilm control, resulting from the combination of different areas (applied microbiology, pharmacognosy, and combinatorial chemistry, molecular biotechnology,</p>

metabolic and bioprocess engineering). WP6 will define a plan of outreach towards the most relevant stakeholders and target groups worldwide, thus creating an impact that will surpass the regional, national and European ties. The project is a unique opportunity for the involved institutions to mutually become internationally top leaders in the emerging and pressing field of antimicrobial drug development for biofilm control. All actors will benefit from being exposed to further collaboration opportunities within the EU and from becoming a critical player in the needed interdisciplinary innovation in antimicrobial development. **TARGET GROUP:** All. **IMPACT:** Scientific, Technologic, Economic, Societal.

4. Communication, dissemination and exploitation of results: main channels and tools

This chapter outlines the tools and channels considered for the implementation of the CDE plan of *InnovAntiBiofilm*. Others may be added if considered relevant and they will be communicated in successive versions of the CDE plan. To ensure joint and consistent communication and contribute to the *InnovAntiBiofilm* objectives, all information or communication support will be centralized by UPORTO and shared with consortium partners for publication.

Table 4. Communication and Dissemination for *InnovAntiBiofilm*

Channels	Details	Target Audience	KPIs
Digital Tools			
Project website <i>Communication</i>	Communication of key information: progress updates, results, events, news, breakthroughs, reports, figures, press releases	All	3.500 visitors
Social media accounts <i>Communication</i>	LinkedIn and Twitter (or X) pages. Partners will also advertise <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i> achievements using their own organisations' pages and social web platforms. A hashtag (<i>#InnovAntiBiofilm</i>) will be created and included in every post	All	500 followers
Events and Networking			
Thematic workshops, summer & winter schools, expert visits <i>Dissemination</i>	Interaction and inputs from different stakeholders, fostering key collaborations, enhance strategic networking actions, spur skills development in metabolic and bioprocess engineering, and medicinal and combinatorial chemistry, and increase knowledge transfer	Biotechnological and Pharmaceutical Professionals, Academia, Students, Researchers, Policy Makers	>140 participants
Staff exchanges <i>Dissemination</i>	<i>In situ</i> visits for an effective transfer of knowledge between partners, fostering collaboration, knowledge sharing, and skill development	Students and Young Researchers	8 participants (6 scientific + 2 admin)
Final symposium <i>Dissemination & Exploitation</i>	Showcase the results and new knowledge generated in <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i> . A platform for in-depth discussions and analysis of the main outcomes, establish links with relevant stakeholder for exploitation, thus strengthening projects and establishing long-lasting collaboration	Biotechnological and Pharmaceutical Professionals, Academia, Students, Researchers, Policy Makers	>100 participants
Participation in external events <i>Dissemination & Exploitation</i>	<i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i> results will be presented in oral communications, posters and special sessions in conferences/exhibitions/fairs. The participation in external events will spur the uptake of results and the establishment of relevant projects.	Biotechnological and Pharmaceutical Industry Professionals, Academia, Students, Researchers, Policy Makers	Participation in 6 conferences, 2 brokerage events, 2 relevant industry events
Communication and Dissemination Channels			
Newsletters, press releases & assorted communication actions <i>Communication</i>	Launch of newsletters every six months to provide an in-depth look at research developments, outcomes and impacts delivered under <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i> , thus promoting a multi-stakeholders engagement by making results public and reachable.	All	200 subscribers 6 newsletters

<p>Promotional materials</p> <p><i>Communication & Dissemination</i></p>	<p>Videos, visual identity, leaflets/brochures, infographics and factsheets (with QR code to promote a more digital approach) to provide general information on the project developments and outcomes to stakeholders. To increase project visibility and promote consistency in C&D.</p>	<p>All</p>	<p>2 videos 2 leaflets 2 infographics</p>
<p>Scientific journals and scientific publications</p> <p><i>Dissemination</i></p>	<p>Vehicle to openly disseminate the knowledge gained during <i>InnovAntiBiofilm</i>. The scientific community will be more aware of the scientific and technological advances. Green and Gold Open Access publishing is foreseen to disseminate scientific knowledge.</p>	<p>Biotechnological and Pharmaceutical Industry Professionals, Academia, Students, Researchers,</p>	<p>12 scientific publications in reputed journals (IF > 7).</p>

If KPI targets are not met during the monitoring period, the consortium will conduct a thorough review to identify underlying barriers and challenges. This process will involve analyzing the effectiveness of current strategies, evaluating resource allocation, and gathering feedback from relevant stakeholders. Based on the findings, the consortium will propose corrective actions to address gaps, which may include adjusting communication approaches, refining dissemination tools, reallocating resources to underperforming areas, or intensifying engagement efforts with specific target groups. These adjustments will be documented and implemented promptly to ensure continuous progress toward achieving the project’s objectives.

4.1. Visual identity and *InnovAntiBiofilm* brand

All the communication tools that are being implemented within the *InnovAntiBiofilm* project share a common **visual identity**. The **visual identity** refers to all the imagery and graphical information that will identify the *InnovAntiBiofilm* project and will differentiate it from all the other initiatives. It provides visual unity to communication material, products and services by establishing a range of colours, typography, templates (Word, PowerPoint) (Figure 2 and 3), pictograms, design elements, images and logo (Figure 4). The development of a “style guide” for the visual identity provides consistent instructions on how the *InnovAntiBiofilm* project should be visually represented at all times and in any situation. All the details about the proper use of the visual identity are presented in a specific document called “Brand manual” (available in the shared folder at OneDrive > “Resources”).

The objectives of a Visual identify for *InnovAntiBiofilm* as regards communication purposes are:

- To guide partners involved in the communication of the project. Partners have to communicate with their country networks and target audiences on a large scale about the activities and the project. Thus, they need guidelines to help them in the use of *InnovAntiBiofilm*’s communication material and to ensure effective external communication.
- To keep clear communication and consistency within the different communication channels: printed material (badge, flyers, roll-up), digital (web, social media), and events mainly.
- To help audiences (stakeholders, end-users, etc) identify the *InnovAntiBiofilm* project, its goals and related activities.

Figure 2. Example of PowerPoint template for InnovAntiBiofilm presentations

4.2. Brand Manual

The brand manual is a document that details the visual identity of a brand which is available in the shared folder at OneDrive > “Resources”. It aims to structure the Project brand with standard graphic elements.

This document is the first step in establishing a framework for the project’s brand. **It has been developed to have some basic elements to support project communication and dissemination development and it presents the rules that must be followed to keep a proper visual identity for the brand.** It will guide the preparation of all communication tools and materials such as the website, documents, flyers, etc.

The brand manual has been submitted to the partners’ review and it will be amended according to emerging needs and required evolutions. The manual and graphic elements are available for all partners and an external version is available on the internet (tool kit).

4.3. Editorial Board

An **Editorial Board** will be set up for the identification, follow-up and implementation of CDE activities. Through these activities, the Editorial Board will provide direction to the overall communication of *InnovAntiBiofilm*.

The Editorial Board is open to all the partners. This board will meet regularly, during monthly consortium meetings, to:

- Organise and update planned CDE activities.
- Submit and discuss the main messages to be communicated according to priorities and tools (website, social media, newsletter).
- Provide partners with advice on content if necessary.
- Inform partners about key messages.
- Attract and encourage other partners' contributions to CDE activities.
- Invite relevant persons to the board for discussion.

With a view to supporting its work, partners will develop a Gantt chart that will define actions, deadlines and progress towards those actions.

4.4. InnovAntiBiofilm Website

A dedicated website is being developed (as of November 2024) to make all information about the project and its actions publicly available. The UPORTO is hosting a webpage accessible with the URL: www.fe.up.pt/innovantibiofilm (Figure 5). It is also possible to find information regarding the *InnovAntiBiofilm* project and ongoing calls on LinkedIn and X.

All partners are actively contributing to the production of content for the website.

Figure 5. Screenshot of InnovAntiBiofilm website available at www.fe.up.pt/innovantibiofilm (under development)

4.4.1. Steps for the website development

The website is being developed in two steps:

- 4.4.1.1. **The launch step:** The first objective of this part is to be able to have an effective tool as soon as possible after the official InnovAntiBiofilm project launch. This launch step will be organized with a simple structure containing all the information required to begin the project.
- 4.4.1.2. **The development step:** This step is intended to complete the previously established structure and offer more information according to the development of the project and the activities related during its lifetime. It will also allow other changes and corrections if they are relevant and identified after the first step launch.

Concerning the structure of the website, the main identified sections are:

- 1 – About the Project (Mission, Problem & Solution)
- 2 – Consortium (Consortium presentation and contribution of each partner)
- 3 – Team (4 sections: Coordinators, Scientific staff, Administrative and Management Staff, Advisory Board)
- 4 – Work Packages
- 5 - Outputs
- 6 – News & Events
- 7 – Contacts

4.4.2. The organization of content and updates

The updates, inclusion and changes to the content of the website are to be made and decided by the Editorial Board. **The Editorial Board** will regularly meet to make decisions regarding the website content. Other partners

with relevant information can directly request updates/inclusion/changes to the Editorial Board. This Editorial Board will also develop and validate the information to be communicated and disseminated on the dedicated channels according to the needs of the editorial policy of the project; this includes updates on the website.

Information regarding *InnovAntiBiofilm* will be updated according to the ongoing activities.

4.5. E-Newsletter

The e-Newsletter enables the *InnovAntiBiofilm* Project to inform the international and national community on relevant information on *InnovAntiBiofilm* ongoing activities, relevant resources initiatives, progress and outcomes, opportunities for researchers, international events held and general news. To feed the e-newsletter, partners will be systematically invited to submit articles and information and to promote them within their local community. The involvement of the *InnovAntiBiofilm* consortium partners in the e-Newsletter is crucial for its success.

4.5.1. The e-Newsletter implementation

Two main steps are required:

1. Creation of the semi-annual e-Newsletter.
 - Develop and manage a network of main contributors (without excluding other contributions)
 - Create a template dedicated to contributors. Text, pictures, and links constitute the main article contents.
 - Receive and compile articles related to *InnovAntiBiofilm* activities and other information.
 - Coordinate the links with people involved in this communication activity.
 - Validate the e-newsletter.
2. Dissemination of the e-Newsletter.

The publication of the full content will be available on the *InnovAntiBiofilm* website. It will be dispatched by e-mail to the registered subscribers by a specific tool at the national and international level on behalf of *InnovAntiBiofilm* members and partners' networks.

4.6. Social media

The social media network aims to enlarge the reach of the *InnovAntiBiofilm* activities amongst different target groups from a specific to a larger audience. It is relevant for the *InnovAntiBiofilm* project to have its own social media profiles and not to only rely on partners' ones to have full control of the message circulating between all types of audiences.

The main social media accounts selected for the *InnovAntiBiofilm* project are LinkedIn and X. The actions related to building a community around social media are:

- Grow in number of followers to be able to reach a large audience.
- Promote their use among the target communities (scientific, stakeholders, citizens, etc).
- Promote them via *InnovAntiBiofilm* partners and existing social media tools. Partners will be required to be active and spread the use of *InnovAntiBiofilm* social media accounts.
- To ensure the continuous dissemination of relevant information via social networks. *InnovAntiBiofilm* consortium members will be requested to continuously update and

publish in each of the above-mentioned social networks.

- All members are invited to support the project communication through their own social media accounts.

The use of X and LinkedIn was decided based on the characteristics of each social media: **LinkedIn** is very professional based where a more technical audience is found. On LinkedIn, more details can be given and messages can be more extensive. **X** is a dynamic social media where information can be disseminated fast (and effectively) in short phrases and in volume.

To ensure the overall coherence of the digital communication strategy and allow a global vision of the messages posted, the Editorial Board will be assigned for the planification and coordination of social media. Some assigned activities for the Editorial Board as regards social media include, but are not limited to:

- To establish or validate the editorial lines
- To decide on the coming events to be shared
- To prepare and validate the messages to be sent
- To create a document to share relevant information with the Consortium members

The messages and content format on social media are designed according to the target audience and available platforms. The different contents available may be:

- | | |
|--|---------------------------------------|
| • Infographics | • Curation of news content |
| • Text (with or without an image) | • Relay content from partners |
| • Information sharing | • Poll/votes |
| • Video: short ones are preferred | • Recycle publications that performed |
| • Storytelling | |
| • Events promotion | |
| • Answer to frequently asked questions | |
| • Quiz game | |

4.7. Events: workshops and meetings

To illustrate key achievements, develop activities and engage with partners and other stakeholders, the *InnovAntiBiofilm* project shall participate in, and promote, different events throughout the years. All thematic public workshops and meetings planned within *InnovAntiBiofilm* will be organized to the highest standard and, whenever possible back-to-back with other activities. With the support of the event organizer and the *InnovAntiBiofilm* Project Coordination Team, relevant information about events will be disseminated via all the channels mentioned in the introductory part of Section 4.

The calendar of *InnovAntiBiofilm* planned events is already defined (Table 5).

Table 5. *InnovAntiBiofilm* planned events

Events/Year	2024	2025	2026	2027
Kick-off/ Status/ Final Meeting	22/10 -23/10 (UPORTO)	3/09 (IME)	08/09 (CEA)	6/09-7/09 (UPORTO)
Monthly Consortium Meetings (online via Teams)	19/11; 10/12	21/01; 18/02; 18/03; 15/04; 20/05; 17/06; 15/07; 19/08; 16/09; 21/10; 18/11; 16/12	20/01; 17/02; 17/03; 21/04; 19/05; 16/06; 21/07; 18/08; 15/09; 20/10; 17/11; 15/12	19/01; 16/02; 16/03; 20/04; 18/05; 15/06; 20/07; 17/08
Workshops	9/12 (UPORTO)	3/09 (IME)	08/09 (CEA)	-
Training Schools (UPORTO)	-	-	02/03-06/03	10/05-14/05
Expert Visit (UPORTO)	9/12-11/12	-	02/03-06/03	10/05-14/05
Final Symposium (UPORTO)	-	-	-	6/09 - 07/09

Some of the international meetings where *InnovAntiBiofilm's* participation may be anticipated include:

- International Congress and Annual Meeting of the Society for Medicinal Plant and Natural Product Research
- ASM/ESCMID Joint Conference on Drug Development to Meet the Challenge of Antimicrobial Resistance
- International Symposium on Pharmaceutical Engineering Research
- ECCMID
- Eurobiofilms
- Biofilms 11

4.8. Preliminary Exploitation Strategy

The Exploitation Strategy, which will be detailed in a Technology Exploitation Roadmap (TER) (D2.2), to be delivered by KPMG by month 36, will evaluate and secure partnerships with private investors, viable funding opportunities, and subsequent R&D projects. This timeline will allow for a comprehensive understanding of the potential of *InnovAntiBiofilm* technology and products, as the scientific and technical results will be available from *InnovAntiBiofilm* WP5 and the final symposium.

The TER will not only assess the potential commercial applications of *InnovAntiBiofilm* solutions but also explore the future utilization of the knowledge acquired during the project. This includes research outcomes that are not commercially exploitable but may provide additional societal and industrial benefits, such as: i) policy briefs/recommendations, ii) enhancement or reinforcement of the participating research groups' capabilities, iii) retention of highly skilled researchers to support ongoing basic and applied research in bioindustry and medicinal chemistry sectors.

A key objective is to ensure a clearly defined and strategic exploitation pathway, ensuring that R&D efforts within the project translate to real-world applications, fostering significant industrial and commercial development opportunities. The definition of exploitation pathways to the industrial sector will be carried out in collaboration with project partners, Advisory Board members, and industry experts/advisors, who will offer

their perspectives and expertise. The main exploitable results and interests are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. The main exploitable results of InnovAntiBiofilm

Partner	Main exploitable results and interests	Value proposition	Main target
UPORTO, IME, CEA	Two innovative molecules for antibiofilm therapy	Patent registration with potential commercial value and spin-off	Biotechnological and Pharmaceutical Industry Professionals; Academia
UPORTO, IME, CEA	Increased transfer of knowledge on antimicrobial development, metabolic and bioprocess engineering, and combinatorial and medicinal chemistry, better serving stakeholders	Further R&D activities, new services, patents, processes and products	Biotechnological and Pharmaceutical Industry Professionals; Academia
UPORTO, IME, CEA	Increase of scientific and technical capacities	Publications in reputed peer-reviewed journals	Academia
UPORTO, IME, CEA	A cross-sectorial national and international collaborative network, capable of collecting industrial needs and developing research	Further R&D activities and new services	Academia
UPORTO, IME, CEA, KPMG	Cooperation with industry	Joint regional (1) and EU projects (3), Memoranda of Understanding (2)	Biotechnological and Pharmaceutical Industry

Collaboration with the industry offers numerous valuable opportunities, including: i) validating research findings, ii) scaling up innovations, iii) speeding up commercialization, iv) gaining access to essential production and distribution channels, v) reaching markets, and vi) aligning research goals with market needs and industry trends. InnovAntiBiofilm aims to harness its R&I potential by establishing meaningful connections with industrial partners. InnovAntiBiofilm will produce a Catalogue of Industrial Stakeholders (D2.1) by month 12, to actively engage with industrial stakeholders to exploit project results while safeguarding intellectual property rights.

This catalogue will i) ensure that industry is invited to project events (workshops, Summer Schools, international symposium), ii) promote additional networking opportunities by attending relevant industry events, conferences, trade shows, and brokerage events (e.g., EU Industry Days, European Research and Innovation Days); iii) develop partnership agreements or memoranda of understanding; iv) actively involve industry partners in the R&D process by leveraging EU-funding programmes and inviting them as partners (e.g., MSCA – Industrial Doctorates); and v) engage with initiatives such as Enterprise Europe Network, EUROPABIO, EuSynBioS, Bio-Based Industries Consortium, and Mu.Ta.Lig. Chemotheca.

5. Protection of Personal Data

As stated in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, all InnovAntiBiofilm partners must conform to the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (“General Data Protection Regulation”), and to its supplementary national legislation for collection and processing of data for which it will be responsible. Associated Parties shall also conform to their national legislation for Data protection.

The participants involved in the communication and dissemination activities described in this plan are varying and can be consortium participants, external Member States and non-Member States participants.

The communication and dissemination activities with potential issues of the Protection of Personal Data (POPD) regulations have been identified and are listed below:

- Meetings (functional, administrative)
- Workshops

- Seminars and conferences (with more external attendees)
- Summer/winter schools
- Mailing lists (communication & dissemination)
- Project website
- Newsletter
- Webinars
- Public presentations at external events (seminars, conferences, meetings, webinars, etc.)
- Additional research activities

To appreciate the low level of POPD issues of this project, it is important to specify that no sensitive personal data are and will be processed. The POPD considerations are limited to information and informed consent of the subjects, and personal data protection concerning (professional) contact information (publicly available) of the subjects.

Respondents to *InnovAntiBiofilm* activities will be given complete information about the processing of their personal data and the procedure for opting out. Their participation is voluntary and their informed consent will be obtained.

6. Following, monitoring and evaluating CDE activities

Effective organization, monitoring, and evaluation of CDE activities are critical to ensuring the project achieves its objectives. Establishing clear timelines and measurable indicators provides a comprehensive overview of completed actions and their impact throughout the project duration.

The monitoring and evaluation process aims to assess the effectiveness of CDE activities using both qualitative and quantitative indicators. Regular evaluation not only verifies progress but also enables the refinement of strategies and processes, ensuring continuous improvement based on feedback and constructive input.

The following sections detail the specific indicators and methodologies for monitoring and evaluating:

- Communication and Dissemination (CD) Activities in section 6.1.
- Exploitation Activities in section 6.2.

6.1. Monitoring and evaluation indicators for CD Activities

Monitoring and evaluating Communication and Dissemination Activities (CDA) is essential to measure the effectiveness of the strategies implemented, ensure alignment with project objectives, and adjust plans as needed. Below, the key quantitative and qualitative indicators are outlined, along with targets and monitoring timelines.

The presented general Table 7 may be adapted more specifically to real needs and possibilities.

The table below outlines the key activities and indicators that will be monitored throughout the project, along with their corresponding evaluation timelines and reporting methods. This structured approach ensures consistency, and transparency in tracking progress against project objectives. Regular monitoring will facilitate the identification of trends, potential challenges, and opportunities for improvement, enabling the consortium to make data-driven adjustments and maintain alignment with expected outcomes.

Quantitative Indicators:

- Social Media Metrics:
 - Number of posts published per month.
 - Audience engagement rates (likes, shares, and comments).
 - Growth in follower count over time.
- Website Analytics:
 - Number of unique visitors annually.
 - Volume of document downloads (e.g., publications, reports).
 - Average time spent on key pages.
- Publications and Presentations:
 - Number of peer-reviewed articles published and conference presentations delivered.
 - Citations of published articles in academic and industry journals.
- Events and Outreach Activities:
 - Number of workshops, webinars, and conferences organized.
 - Attendance rates and diversity of participants (e.g., representation from academia, industry, and policymakers).

Qualitative Indicators:

- Content Quality and Relevance: Feedback from target audiences on clarity, relevance, and usefulness of communication materials (collected via surveys or interviews).
- Audience Engagement: Survey results measuring understanding of key messages and interest in project outcomes.

Regular evaluations will be conducted to track progress against the identified indicators. The schedule for monitoring and reporting is outlined in Table 7. Monitoring results will inform adjustments to CD Activities strategies. If targets are not met, the consortium will:

- Identify barriers to success through ad-hoc reviews.
- Implement corrective actions, such as refining messaging, reallocating resources, or intensifying engagement efforts.
- Document changes and reassess progress during the next evaluation cycle.

By systematically monitoring and evaluating CD Activities indicators, InnovAntiBiofilm will ensure that these activities remain effective and impactful throughout the project lifecycle.

6.2. Monitoring and evaluating exploitation activities

The exploitation of *InnovAntiBiofilm's* results is central to ensuring the project's impact extends beyond its duration, creating tangible benefits for commercial, societal, and political purposes. Exploitation activities aim to ensure that significant results are not only recognized but actively utilized during the project lifecycle and after its completion. Given the diverse range of activities and outputs foreseen by InnovAntiBiofilm, exploitation efforts will be tailored to the nature of the results, their target users, the partners responsible for their transfer, timelines, and available resources. Monitoring and evaluating these activities will ensure continuous alignment with project objectives and stakeholder needs.

To maximize the impact of project results, several exploitation methods will be implemented. Policy recommendations will be sought and disseminated through potential actionable policy briefs targeting both EU and national policymakers. The project's scientific contributions will be shared via peer-reviewed publications and presentations at international conferences. Horizon Europe exploitation tools, such as the Horizon Results Booster, Horizon Results Platform, and Innovation Radar, will be leveraged to enhance the visibility and scalability of the project's outcomes. Additionally, knowledge sharing and networking will be facilitated through the establishment of dedicated platforms, including industry networks and domain-specific hubs, to engage stakeholders and foster collaboration.

Specific actions will be taken to promote project results among relevant communities. These include the identification of stakeholders, both within the project and across external networks, who can directly benefit from the project's outputs. Efforts will be made to facilitate third-party exploitation by providing stakeholders and collaborators with tools, documentation, and guidance to make use of project results. Effective communication channels will be utilized to engage potential users, including stakeholder networks, project websites, domain-specific platforms, and social media. Continuous market trend analysis will ensure project outputs remain aligned with emerging demands in relevant fields.

This structured approach to exploitation will ensure that InnovAntiBiofilm's results are effectively disseminated, adopted, and utilized, creating sustainable impact across multiple sectors. Regular monitoring and evaluation will provide the necessary insights to adapt and optimize exploitation strategies, maximizing the project's long-term value.

Evaluation Framework & Timelines

Evaluation of exploitation activities is critical for identifying their strengths, weaknesses, and overall performance. This will ensure outputs are not only disseminated but adopted effectively. The performance of

exploitation activities will be measured using both qualitative and quantitative indicators, described in Table 7.

To ensure effective tracking, exploitation activities will be monitored and evaluated at regular intervals:

- Quarterly: Assessment of stakeholder engagement and dissemination reach.
- Biannually: Review of scientific publications, and new collaborations.
- Annually: Comprehensive evaluation of adoption metrics and market alignment.

Table 7. InnovAntiBiofilm's identified indicators for the evaluation of CED activities

		No. of new posts	No. time spent on page	No. of new visitors	No. visits, clicks or views	No. shares, likes and comments	No. of subscribers/ Participants	No. docs or data downloaded	Different Countries reached	No. articles or documents delivered	No. of events held/ participated	No. of feedback scores	No of new projects, collaborations, or initiatives	Monitoring Frequency
Digital communication (Project / Activities)	Website InnovAntiBiofilm	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X				Quarterly
	E-newsletter	X		X	X		X		X					
	Platforms	X				X	X	X	X					
	Press releases	X			X	X			X	X				
Social Media (Project / Activities)	X	X		X	X	X	X		X					Quarterly
	LinkedIn	X		X	X	X	X		X					
Events (Project / Activities)	Meetings, workshops			X			X			X	X	X	X	Biannually
	Webinars			X			X		X	X	X	X	X	
	Networks / European, International events						X				X	X	X	
Printable & digital docs (Project / Activities)	Leaflets, flyers, booklets							X		X				Biannually
	Policy briefs							X		X		X		
	Posters									X				
Classic media (Press / Radio)	Press releases	X							X	X				Annually
	Articles	X				X			X	X				
	Interviews	X							X	X	X			

Conclusion

This document defines all the *InnovAntiBiofilm* strategies for **CDE plan** along the project development, through the leadership of UPORTO and with active participation from all project partners, as defined in the Work Package 6.

This document shall be revised and updated through *InnovAntiBiofilm* execution period by the Editorial Board. Updated versions of this document will be accessible to all project partners in the shared folder in OneDrive “Work Packages and Deliverables”.

The main channels and tools for **CDE** are defined and described in this plan. The visual identity and the brand manual are presented, ensuring a uniform and consolidate image for project documents, communication and events. The role of the editorial board is defined, and their regular discussion is planned at each monthly consortium meeting. The main channels defined for project dissemination and communication outside the consortium are the project website (www.fe.up.pt/innovantibiofilm), periodic newsletters, social media (LinkedIn and X). All the planned *InnovAntiBiofilm* events are already scheduled, and the respective calendar and partner organizer is defined in this **CDE plan**. Moreover, the preliminary *InnovAntiBiofilm* exploitation strategy is also presented, defining strategies for the evaluation and securing partnerships with private investors, viable funding opportunities, and subsequent R&D projects. However, detailed information on exploitation strategy will be made available in D2.2 - Technology Exploitation Roadmap.

Quantitative indicators and periodicity for monitoring and evaluation of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities are also defined in the current version of the **CDE plan**.

References

The main references are:

[Regulation \(EU\) No 1290/20138 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013](#)

[Voluntary Guidelines on framework conditions for joint programming in research 2010](#)

European IPR Helpdesk Making the most of your Horizon 2020 Project – EU 2018

[RDIEU Grants: Horizon 2020 Guidance Social media guide for EU funded RDI projects, 2020 Guidelines on](#)

[Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020](#) EU open data - The basics for EU data providers – EU Open data Portal- Edition 2016